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Building A 175-Year Record of Vertical Land Motion in the Coos Bay, Oregon, Area From Repeated Leveling, Tide Gauge Records, and INSAR to Characterize Cascadia Strain and Sea Level Rise

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ABSTRACT

Subduction zone earthquakes are a major geologic hazard that impact the American West Coast (California, Washington, and Oregon). These quakes originate from a fault zone known as the Cascadia Subduction Zone, or CSZ. In the CSZ, the denser oceanic Juan de Fuca Plate is subducting beneath the less dense continental North American Plate. This movement causes strain to build up in the CSZ as plates converge and the coast uplifts, which will be released during a subsequent megathrust quake.

The last major subduction zone earthquake to impact the Oregon Coast occurred in 1700; it is difficult to determine exactly when another such earthquake will occur. Our study aims to provide a timeline of strain buildup starting relatively soon after the 1700 earthquake, which can offer valuable insight into how the CSZ behaves. Our research primarily focuses on gaining a deeper understanding of how strain has accumulated along the Oregon Coast over the past 175 years in the form of vertical land motion, with the goal of better defining the seismic hazard faced by millions of people in the Pacific Northwest.

To begin the process of characterizing coastal uplift in this area, we have assembled and organized both sea level data, collected using tidal gauges, and land leveling data, collected using first- and second-order surveying, over the past 175 years in the Coos Bay, OR, area into an online database. As survey elevation data is based on the mean sea level, we utilize both these data points to develop a more accurate model for true uplift rate and subduction zone strain along the CSZ in this region. The primary objective of this project is to compile the necessary data to determine both relative (local) and absolute (within a global reference frame) vertical land motion and sea level changes, thereby addressing tectonic activity and sea level rise.

INTRODUCTION

The Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) is a major subduction zone that runs along the west coast of North America from California to British Columbia, and it poses a significant seismic threat to the region. Here, the Juan de Fuca Plate is subducting underneath the North American Plate; as a result of this process, areas along the CSZ experience uplift in conjunction with interseismic locking or straining. However, this uplifting and straining does not occur uniformly across the entire region, which makes quantifying these factors incredibly difficult. Many

past studies, which will be discussed further in the background section of this paper, focus on the American West Coast and seek to better characterize uplift rates through the use of historical tidal gauge and land leveling data.

One of these approaches is to relate tidal gauge records to land leveling (benchmark) data, each of which helps to contextualize the other. Primarily, researchers have utilized mean water level measurements and hourly tidal height observations in addition to repeated first- and second-order highway leveling surveys when comparing these data points. The tidal data reveal how fast water levels are rising, and the land leveling data show the rate at which the coast is uplifting (Burgette et al., 2009). Neither of these two data sets can provide an accurate uplift estimate on its own; utilizing multiple data points helps account for leveling errors that are often caused by benchmark instability due to subsidence or setting damage. Ideally, a relatively stable group of benchmarks set in bedrock will be used. Then, these benchmarks can be tied to regional leveling lines, enabling researchers to put them in an absolute reference frame, thus allowing the calculation of absolute sea level change and a measure of vertical land motion. By comparing these values across a region and through time, researchers can estimate the relative rate at which the Oregon coast is uplifting, which provides valuable insight into how seismic strain is accumulating in the CSZ.

Both historical and modern tidal and land leveling data are available in abundance for locations along the Oregon coast, making this approach viable for characterizing uplift rates in the region. We have found records dating back to the 1850s that are relevant to our primary study area, which stretches from Charleston, OR, to Coos Bay/North Bend, OR. Thus, we can utilize these records to better understand how uplift is occurring in our region and to help quantify the seismic risks associated with this section of the CSZ. We have approached this project by organizing available historical data into an online database. In the future, we will analyze this data by performing adjustments to the data to negate errors and creating plots or figures to visualize uplift patterns. Our research is an extension of past work done along larger stretches of the West coast; thus, it will be presented within the context of these prior projects. Many of these prior projects utilize data from the 1930s or 1970s; the next key step in continuing this work is to extend the record back in time using earlier data.

BACKGROUND

Uplift rates along the CSZ have been studied extensively throughout time using a variety of approaches. However, studies that specifically utilize historical tidal gauge and land leveling data to understand this phenomenon have been conducted more recently, starting around the early 1990s; a large portion of these scientific publications focus their research on the American West Coast.

Early work done in 1994 by Clifton E. Mitchell and his colleagues, including Twinning mentor Ray Weldon, establishes a broad study area across the entire American West Coast. Their research, comparisons of tidal gauge and repeated land leveling data from the 1920s to 1980s, summarized in the form of a contour map that depicts present-day uplift rates for the western Pacific Northwest, indicates that “much of the western Pacific Northwest is rising at rates between 0 and 5 mm/yr” (Mitchell et al., 1994). A similar project focusing on the entire American West Coast was conducted by D. Schmidt, Ray Weldon, Reed Burgette, and Randy Krogstad in 2011. This project involved “invert[ing] historical leveling, tide gauge, and contemporary GPS observations for a distributed backslip model of strain accumulation on the locked subduction interface,” taking a closely related approach to understanding uplift as previous studies (D. Schmidt et al., 2011).

While these studies included data from the entire American West Coast, many other projects focus on a specific region within this broader area. Oregon and Washington, in particular, have been the subject of continued subduction zone research. The previously mentioned 2009 paper by Burgette et al. narrows its study area to Northern California and the Oregon coast while expanding the amount of data it considers, including tidal and leveling data from 1925 to 2006. Another study, done by Randy Krogstad et al. in 2016, “use[s] uplift rates from

leveling campaigns spanning approximately 50–70 [years] in Washington and Oregon” to investigate long-term locking in the CSZ. Furthermore, certain studies only focus on analyzing uplift rates in a single state, like the work done by Sequoia Alba and her colleagues in 2011. Her research investigates “vertical displacements, uplift rates between events, and net uplift rates” between 1997 and 2010 using “hourly water level records from 4 NOAA [National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration] tide gauges” (Alba et al., 2011). While individual studies on CSZ uplift using tidal and leveling data address how the phenomenon occurs over different periods of time in different regions, they all contribute to an overall understanding of how uplift occurs along this subduction zone.

As all previous studies using this methodology refer to tidal gauge data and land leveling data, it is important to understand what information is contained in these datasets. Tidal gauge data can consist of multiple types of water level data, but it usually includes some kind of elevation reading above a specific, established marker, like mean water level, lower low water level, or a primary benchmark. Tidal data can span multiple timeframes as well, recorded with up to hourly precision. Land leveling data is fairly complex and is categorized by order and class, which indicate what procedures were followed and the amount of measuring error allowed. For this research, we utilize first-, second-, and third-order leveling, with first-order data being the most precise.

While the previously mentioned studies help establish and refine this particular research methodology, there are still gaps in the data considered, both historical and modern, which consequently affect the overall uplift timeline. Our continuation of this research aims to help support and extend existing studies by creating an organized digital database for files relevant to the methodology used. In the future, we hope to address these time and data gaps by collecting our own tidal and leveling data and analyzing existing data for the area that dates back to the 1850s.

METHODS AND RESULTS

Collecting and Organizing Data

Since this project has been ongoing for several decades, the primary purpose of my contributions to this research was to collect and organize the wealth of already existing relevant data into an online database. To do so, I began by assessing the files that we already had access to. This assortment of files, comprising both digital and physical documents, originates from various sources, spans locations from California to British Columbia, and ranges from the 1850s to the present day. Initially, I collected any data referencing the American West Coast, but as the project progressed, I focused my efforts on data that specifically concerned our study area.

Collecting the digital files was a simple process; they originated from only a few sources. First, I pulled publicly available tidal station data, including station reports and latitude and longitude points, from the NOAA Tides and Currents online database and saved them to a designated folder on my computer. The next set of files I collected was sent to me via email by Reed Burgette. His extensive work on the Charleston and

Figure 1. Map of benchmarks in Coos Bay area during 1931-1988 deployment.

Empire areas of the Oregon Coast is a valuable addition to our database, since it primarily focuses on our study area. During his time on the project, he produced multiple Excel spreadsheets containing latitude and longitude points, differenced uplift values, and made notes for future work. I saved these files in their own separate folder on my computer and developed a map of the benchmarks within our study area using Google Maps and Canva from the provided coordinate points (See Fig.1). I was also emailed tidal station and water level reports that were scanned by other undergraduate Earth Science students, which I saved onto my computer. Finally, I transferred files from an external hard drive to my own computer. These files consisted of tidal station and water level reports, as well as INSAR (Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar) figures that show ground deformation by using radar images of Earth's surface.

The physical files were more difficult to work with due to their sheer volume. This data was collected or created throughout the project's multi-decade lifetime and was stored in a filing cabinet. Over the course of three and a half weeks, I scanned around 1,500 pages from various paper documents. Within these files were tidal station reports, water level data, both professionally created and hand-drawn maps, theses on related subjects, handwritten notes, and leveling data. After scanning the documents, I reviewed each of the files, gave them specific and descriptive names, and saved them to my computer.

Creating a Database and Associated Inventory

To organize the files I had collected and saved to my personal computer, I used OneDrive, a cloud-based file service created by Microsoft. I created a main folder with multiple subfolders to make the data easier to navigate. Within the master folder, I created unique folders for Washington, Oregon, and California; for files that were relevant to multiple states, I put them into their own separate folder. (See Fig. 2) After sorting the files by state, I focused on the Oregon folder and created subfolders for different cities/regions (See Fig. 2). The files most relevant to our current research in the Coos Bay Area were given their own folder that includes further subfolders broken up by location.

Figure 2. State database folders (left column) and Oregon regional folders (right column).

File Name and Location	Data Location	Dates	Benchmarks Included	Location Code	Water Level Data	Leveling Data	Ties	Notes
943-2864 Empire OR	(Page 1-5)	May 27, 1922 - February 2, 1988	4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8A, 8B, 9, 10	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean tide level
OR, Coos Bay Area, Empire Sub-Folder	(Page 6-13)	October 18, 1976 - February 2, 1988	North Base, L-B, 3	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water
	(Page 14)	February 2, 1988 - March 30, 1988	4, 7, 9, 10, North Base	943-2864	N/A	Yes, 4.0 mm, 1st Order	?	Unadjusted elevations
	(Page 15-16)	December 21-22, 1976; October 18, 1976	3A, 3B, North Base, 9, 10	943-2864	N/A	Yes, 3rd Order	?	Abstract of precise levels
	(Page 17)	November-December 1976	Tidal 3 1976, 9 1924, 10 1924, North Base, L-B	943-2864	Yes	N/A	Control Tidal Station - Charleston (943 2780)	
	(Page 19-20)	June 1, 1922 - May 1923	4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean tide level
	(Page 23-24)	April 22, 1969	4, 7, 8, 9	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water, based on data from June 1922 - May 1923
	(Page 26)	February 20, 1948	4, 5, 6, 7, 8	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water
	(Page 27)	October 8, 1946	4, 6, 7, 8	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water
	(Page 29)	March 15, 1927	4, 5, 6, 7, 8	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water and mean tide level
	(Page 30)	August 26, 1926	4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water and mean tide level
	(Page 31)	April 26, 1924	1, 4, 5, 6	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water and mean tide level
	(Page 32)	May 21, 1927	4, 5, 6	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water and mean tide level
	(Page 33)	October 16, 1913	1, 2, 3	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevations based on staff readings from 1880, tide planes
	(Page 34)	February 23, 1906	1, 2, 3	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation readings above zero of tide staff
	(Page 37-41) ?	?	9, 10	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water and half tide level
	(Page 55)	1880-1924	1, 4	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Mean sea level, lowest tide
	(Page 58)	December 1, 1976	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	High and low water, Charleston
	(Page 61)	May - November 1924	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Summary of automatic tide gauge observations
	(Page 65-66)	1922-1923	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Tides: monthly means, differences
	(Page 67)	June 12-18, 1924	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Tides: hourly heights
	(Page 68)	May 27, 1924 - November 10, 1924	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Tides: monthly means
	(Page 69)	May 29, 1924 - November 9, 1924	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Tides: comparison of monthly means
	(Page 70)	1880	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Mean high and low water
	(Page 71-72)	1880	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Tides: first reduction
	(Page 73-77)	1880-1881	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Gauge readings: high and low water
	(Page 78-89)	January-November 1881	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Daily tides; first reduction
	(Page 90-96)	May 8 - June 30, 1890	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Daily tides; first reduction
File Name and Location	Data Location	Dates	Benchmarks Included	Location Code	Water Level Data	Leveling Data	Ties	Notes
943-2864 Empire OR p2	(Page 1-24)	May 29 - November 24, 1924	Tide Gauge No. 121	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Tides: hourly heights
OR, Coos Bay Area, Empire Sub-Folder	(Page 25-32)	October 23, 1976 - January 5, 1977	?	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Tides: hourly heights
	(Page 33-86)	May 27, 1922 - June 2, 1923	Tide Gauge No. 108	943-2864	Yes	N/A	?	Tides: hourly heights
File Name and Location	Data Location	Dates	Benchmarks Included	Location Code	Water Level Data	Leveling Data	Ties	Notes
Empire Quadrangle, Vertical Control	(Page 1-2)	?	K468, L468, Y79, M468, Z79, P468, E286, F286, G286, H286, 573	N/A	N/A	Yes, 1st Order	?	Unadjusted elevations
OR, Coos Bay Area, Empire Sub-Folder	(Page 2-4)	?	1, 2, 3, 4 (1928), 5 (1933), 4, (1922) 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10	N/A	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water, mean sea level, and half tide level
File Name and Location	Data Location	Dates	Benchmarks Included	Location Code	Water Level Data	Leveling Data	Ties	Notes
Empire Tidal Benchmark List and Map (1922-1923)	(Page 2)	June 1, 1922 - May 1923	9, 10	N/A	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water and mean tide level
OR, Coos Bay Area, Empire Sub-Folder								
File Name and Location	Data Location	Dates	Benchmarks Included	Location Code	Water Level Data	Leveling Data	Ties	Notes
Empire, Coos Bay - Tidal Benchmark List and Map (1922-1923)	(Page 2)	March 15, 1927	9, 10	N/A	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water and mean tide level
OR, Coos Bay Area, Empire Sub-Folder	(Page 3)	March 15, 1928	4, 5, 6, 7, 8	N/A	Yes	N/A	?	Elevation above mean lower low water and mean tide level

Figure 3. Empire page of inventory Excel spreadsheet.

Following the collection and organization process, we began to review and inventory our data. Although the online database is easier to navigate than the previous file organization system, it still proved challenging to identify essential data for our current project iteration and to relate multiple data points to one another. Thus, I created an Excel spreadsheet inventorying the different files saved within each of the Coos Bay Area subfolders. This inventory list consists of individual sheets for the Charleston, Empire, and Marshfield area subfolders; the Burgette files are also included on their own sheet. Each sheet (see Fig. 3) breaks down the contents of the subfolders, including what benchmarks are mentioned, if water level or leveling data is present, if a NOAA station code is associated with the data, and any potential ties between different locations; it also records where the information is found in each file. This Excel file is also saved to the OneDrive database to aid future researchers in understanding what data we currently have and where this data can be found. This process provides insight into what data, if any, we will still need to request from NOAA.

Additional Data Collection Efforts

While the database and Excel spreadsheet I created include files that were readily available to us, there are additional files we would like to add to them. Primarily, NOAA may have more relevant files that would be invaluable to include in our collection. These files could fill in the gaps between the data we currently have, making it easier to connect different tidal gauge stations and relate them to land leveling reports, which is an essential step in characterizing uplift rates. Furthermore, we initially planned to deploy our own tidal gauge/s in the Coos Bay Area to continue to build upon existing tidal data. Both attempts to collect additional historical data or create new datasets were unsuccessful, as we were unable to get in contact with the proper NOAA employees and several Coos Bay landowners, whose permission we would require to deploy a gauge.

DISCUSSION

The creation of an online database for a decades-long, ongoing research project that relies heavily on multiple forms of historical and modern data will benefit the work of future researchers who want to study the uplift rate and vertical land motion of the Cascadia Subduction Zone using tidal gauge and land leveling data. In particular, this data organization effort will support the continuation of research in our study area around Coos Bay, OR, by simplifying document navigation. This project has spanned many years, leading to a data “backlog.” Consequently, some data may be misplaced or forgotten about, especially when it exists in both digital and physical formats. Organization is key when dealing with this large a volume of documents. To proceed with the analysis of data from our study area, we first needed to assess what documentation is available to us. This allowed us to identify any remaining data gaps and narrow down the list of data we needed to request from external sources.

While the online database may streamline the data location and analysis process for future researchers, it certainly has gaps where essential data may be missing. The current dataset stored in our database likely does not include all relevant existing data on our research topic, but there is no way to know if or where this data exists and how to acquire it. By no means is this database complete; it has the potential to be constantly added to or revised. However, it can be difficult to gather new data without the active cooperation of private businesses, local land owners, or government systems, which contributes to the incomplete nature of this database. Therefore, future researchers should keep these limitations in mind when developing a research plan and accessing and utilizing this database. We encourage the use of this database in future projects focusing on uplift on the American West Coast, but we also recognize that this research method could be potentially useful in studying other active subduction zones for which historical tidal gauge and land leveling data exist.

Following the completion of this part of the overarching CSZ uplift project, we hope to analyze the data we have compiled for Charleston and Empire by looking for overlap in deployment dates, which will allow us to tie

together different datasets and begin to assess uplift rates in this particular region. Even a week of properly tied data would give us enough information to generate an accurate long-term uplift trend after removing regional noise.

CONCLUSION

Research into how tidal gauge and land leveling data can help characterize the strain building in the CSZ to assess seismic risk along the American West Coast has been ongoing for decades; our project is an extension of this previous work. While we did not have the opportunity to add new information to existing historical data, we moved this project forward by collecting and organizing relevant digital and physical files into an accessible online database. In addition, we created a simplified navigation system for the 175 years of data that concern our study area by building an inventory for the files we compiled. These organizational efforts will aid future researchers in parsing through the large volume of existing historical data to find information valuable to the particular parameters of subsequent studies.

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